

Energy Shifts and Kaniadakis Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell July 7, 2018

Recently, Kaniadakis [1] proposed a new statistical distribution for relativistic particles. His expression becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution under nonrelativistic conditions. It is interesting to note, however, that the MB distribution is not affected by a constant shift in the value of energy. If energy goes from E to $E+b$ the (MB) distribution $\exp(-E/T)/C$, where C is a normalization constant, stays unchanged. It is further interesting to note that the MB distribution can be obtained through a variational calculation of:

$\sum f_i \ln(f_i) - w (\sum e_i f_i)$ with $\sum f_i = 1$ and $\sum e_i f_i = E/N$ where E is the total energy and N the total number of particles and w a Lagrange multiplier. Now, the energy constraint can be shifted to give a new constraint $\sum (e_i - b) f_i = E/N - b$. Using this in a variational calculation would give a distribution proportional to $\exp(-(e_i - b)/T)$, but this should not lead to any physical changes. In addition, examining the microcanonical distribution seems to indicate that a shift in energy should not change the number of states or the probability distribution. Curiously, the distribution given by Kaniadakis does not appear to be invariant under a shift in energy. The purpose of this note is to examine energy shift and to see if there is a simple way to add this invariance to the Kaniadakis distribution..

Microcanonical Distribution

Consider a system with allowable energy levels e_i such that $\sum n_i e_i = E$. Here n_i is the number of particles with energy e_i and E the total energy. One can tabulate all possible sets of n_i . Now consider subtracting (or adding b) to each e_i and Nb to E . Then every set of n_i is a solution of the new problem. Thus, it seems that shifting all energies by a constant amount does not change the overall entropy or probability to have a particle with energy e_i .

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is given by $f_i = \exp(-e_i/T)/C$ where $C = \sum \exp(-e_j/T)$ with a sum on j . Thus, adding or subtracting b from e_i will cancel with the b added to all of the e_j 's in the denominator. The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is invariant under the addition or subtraction of a constant to each energy value.

Variational Principles

Both the Kaniadakis [1] and the MB distributions can be obtained from a variational principle. In each case one varies the entropy subject to an energy constraint. The energy constraint is usually taken as $\sum e_i f_i = E/N$ where E is the total energy and N the total number of particles.

It seems, however, that one can alter the form of the energy constraint. For example, one can add

$b = \sum b f_i$ to each side because $\sum f_i = 1$. Then the constraint becomes $\sum (e_i + b) f_i = E/N + b$.

The variable in question in the variational calculation is now $e_i + b$, not e_i . Let us consider the MB case as an example. The function to be varied is

$\sum [f_i \ln(f_i) - f_i] + w \sum (e_i + b) f_i$ This yields f_i proportional to $\exp(-(e_i + b)/T)$.

Introducing a normalization constant eliminates b from the solution.

Kaniadakis [1] also uses a variational principle, but a different expression for entropy. He shows that if $d s/d f = G(f)$ where $s = \text{entropy density}$ i.e. $S = [\text{Integral } s \, d f]$ then the variational principle leads to:

$G(f_i) = -w(e_i + b)$ or $f_i = G^{-1}(e_i + b)$ In general, $G^{-1}(e_i + b)$ is not equal to $G(e_i)$ even when normalization is added. We will examine the case for Kaniadakis' distribution.

Energy Shifts and the Kaniadakis' Distribution

The Kaniadakis [1] distribution is given by:

$f_i = \{ \sqrt{1 + (kE/T)^2} + kE/T \}^{1/k}$ where $1/k = \text{rest mass}$. This is not normalized. In the limit of k going to zero the term $(kE/T)^2$ vanishes and one is left with a common limit for the exponential function. Thus, one obtains the MB distribution. It appears, however, that if one shifts E from E to $E + b$, one has changed the distribution. Consider:

$Z = (f(e_1 + b)/f(e_2 + b))^k$ This expression should be equal to $(f(e_1)/f(e_2))^k$ if b is not a factor. In addition, T which is physical temperature should be the same in both cases.

In such a case $(f(e_1 + b)/f(e_2 + b))^k$ should not contain b or the derivative with respect to b should vanish. Here below g is f with the exponent $1/k$ removed.

$dZ/db = -g_1 g_2' / g_2^2 + g_1' / g_2$ so $-g_1 g_2' + g_1' g_2$ should equal 0.

Now $g_1' = (k/T) g_1 / [\sqrt{1 + (k/T)(e_1 + b)^2}]$ and a similar expression for g_2'

So having the derivative equal 0 implies:

$[\sqrt{1 + (k/T)(e_1 + b)^2}] = [\sqrt{1 + (k/T)(e_2 + b)^2}]$

Which is not the case.

Relevance of an Energy Shifted Distribution

At this point, one many inquire into the physical relevance of an energy shifted distribution in the first place. In a gas, one has many different energy values e_i , but there are also many cases where $e_i - e_j = b$ for different values of i and j . In the MB case, the distribution ratio for all of these cases is the same even though they have different e_i and e_j values. If one were to develop some ideas based on relative probabilities, then one would want distributions which are not affected by energy shifts.

Possible Way to Make a Kaniadakis Distribution Invariant under a Constant Energy Shift

A very simple way to make the Kaniadakis distribution invariant under a constant energy shift is to add a cutoff energy i.e. to replace E with $E - E_{\text{cutoff}}$. Then adding an energy shift to E and E_{cutoff} cancel each other. Of course, one would need to see if this can be made to match experimental data, because the Kaniadakis distribution was implemented in the first place to fit the non Maxwell-Boltzmann tail of relativistic particles.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it appears that the Kaniadakis distribution for relativistic particles is not invariant under an energy shift i.e. changing the relativistic particle energy from E to $E + b$. The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is, however, invariant in such a case. Furthermore, the microcanonical distribution seems to imply that such an invariance should exist. A problem seems to arise because the Kaniadakis distribution can be obtained from a variational principle with an energy constraint. It is possible to shift this energy constraint and thus obtain a solution of $f(e_i)$ and another with $f(e_i + b)$. One would expect these to be the same as they are describing the same physical situation, but this does not appear to happen with the Kaniadakis expression. One could, however, replace E with $E - E_{\text{cutoff}}$ in the expressions of Kaniadakis and then there would be no problem. There is, however, the question whether such an approach would still allow the Kaniadakis results to match experimental ones.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Relativistic Kinetics and Power Tailed Distributions 2010.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/48169936_Relativistic_kinetics_and_power-law_tailed_distributions